

Image registration based on Modified Complement Weighted Sum of Minimal Distance

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Abstract—We propose a novel distance measure called Modified Complement Weighted Sum of Minimal Distance (MCWSMD) for image registration. We have conducted experiments by adding different types of noise on the grayscale images, medical images and on the face dataset. We further evaluated performance on synthetic images and then compared the results with other existing methods and found that MCWSMD outperforms the other distance based methods.

Index Terms—Image registration, Distance measure, Face recognition, Set distance

I. INTRODUCTION

Image registration is the process of aligning two images that share common visual information that can be taken at different times or using different sensors or at different geometric view points. It is an essential step in the image processing application. The main objective of the image registration is to find the geometric transformation that maps the source image into the target image. In this paper we study the registration problem with reference to translation and rotation of the images, using distance measures.

Hatimi et al. [1] proposed an approach to track the moving object using a fixed camera. Daway et al. [2] proposed a new strategy to precise pupil detection. Edy et al. [3] proposed a model of face recognition utilizing the asymmetrical half-join method for joining two face images from left and right lens from a stereo vision camera.

The distance measure is one of the important tools to determine the correspondence between the images in order to quantify the accuracy of the image registration. Researchers have proposed a number of distance measures for different applications and problems [4]-[19]. The Hausdorff distance and its modifications are used for image registration and related problems [4]-[5], [7]-[18]. Barrow et al. [4] have proposed parametric correspondence and chamfer matching for image matching. Hierarchical chamfer matching was developed by Borgfors [5] and it was used widely in various applications of image processing. Huttenlocher et al. [6] have presented algorithms for computing the Hausdorff distance between a binary image and a model. Dubussion and Jain [7] presented a modified Hausdorff distance (MHD) based on the average distance value for object matching. Eiter and Mannila [8] introduced sum of minimal distance and it is very much

useful in various applications such as computational geometry, updating or changing theories, philosophy of science and in machine learning. Object location using Hausdorff distance was presented by Rucklidge [9]. Jesorsky et al. [10] presented a face detection system using Hausdorff distance. Kwon et al. [11] proposed hierarchical Hausdorff distance matching algorithms using pyramidal structures. Weighted Hausdorff distance for word image matching was proposed by Lu et al. [12].

A new Hausdorff distance measure was proposed by Zhao et al. [13] for gray images that have a few pixel values. Zwang et al. [14] have used generalised and mean Hausdorff distance for character recognition. Zachow et al. [15] have used Hausdorff distance measure in computer-assisted planning for improved surgical preparation. Espinace et al. [16] have used Modified Hausdorff Distance in robot movements by finding the distance between the expected line segments the robot should sense and the line segments extracted from actual measurements using a range finder. Ji et al. [17] proposed Hausdorff distance based matching for outdoor mobile robot localisation. Recently Čurić et al. [18] proposed complement weighted sum of minimal distance in which they combined good properties of sum of minimal distance and included the information from the complement of sets. This distance measure performs well for the binary images. When complement weighted sum of minimal distance is applied to register the grayscale and medical images, the performance is low. In order to overcome the problem, we proposed a new distance measure and use binary images, grayscale images, medical images and also images on a face dataset to test its performance in the image registration. The objective of proposed distance measure to provide an efficient way to register the image even in the presence of noise.

In this paper we propose a novel measure called Modified complement weighted sum of minimal distance (MCWSMD) and compared it with existing measures. The proposed distance measure is able to determine the correspondence among the images. The results are compared with Čurić et al. [18] results. This distance measure is developed in order to improve the performance of registration of translated and rotated images. This paper is organised as follow as: the basic definition on Hausdorff distance is presented in Section II. We define Modi-

fied complement weighted sum of minimal distance measure in Section III. Experimental results are discussed in Section IV. The concluding remarks are presented in Section V.

II. OVERVIEW OF HAUSDORFF DISTANCE

In this section we review Hausdorff distance and its properties briefly.

A. Hausdorff distance

The distance measure between the set of the points is an important task in image analysis. The distance between the two points a and b is defined as:

$$\Delta(a, b) = \| a - b \| \quad (1)$$

The distance between a point a and a finite set of points $B = \{b_1, b_2, \dots, b_{N_b}\}$ is commonly defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta(a, B) &= \min_{b \in B} \Delta(a, b) \\ &= \min_{b \in B} \| a - b \| \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Distance $\Delta : S_1 \times S_2 \rightarrow R^+$ is a metric if it satisfies the following properties, for $A, B, C \in S_1 \times S_2$

Property 1 Non negativity:

$$\Delta(A, B) \geq 0$$

Property 2 Symmetry:

$$\Delta(A, B) = \Delta(B, A) \text{ for any } A \text{ and } B$$

Property 3 Positive definiteness:

$$\Delta(A, B) = 0 \text{ if and only if } A = B$$

Property 4 Triangle inequality:

$$\Delta(A, B) \leq \Delta(A, C) + \Delta(C, B) \text{ for any } A, B \text{ and } C$$

If $S_1 = S_2 = R^n$, the most commonly used metrics are Euclidean distance, City block, and Chessboard. These three distance measures are popularly used in pattern recognition and in image processing applications. We use Euclidean distance.

The set distance was proposed by Felix Hausdorff [19]. The use of Hausdorff distance for binary image comparison and computer vision was proposed by Huttenlocher et al. [6]. The distance $\Delta(A, B)$ between two finite point sets $A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{N_a}\}$ and $B = \{b_1, b_2, \dots, b_{N_b}\}$ is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta(A, B) &= \max_{a \in A} \Delta(a, B) \\ &= \max_{a \in A} \min_{b \in B} \Delta(a, b) \\ &= \max_{a \in A} \min_{b \in B} \| a - b \| \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

In this way $\Delta(B, A)$ is

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta(B, A) &= \max_{b \in B} \Delta(b, A) \\ &= \max_{b \in B} \min_{a \in A} \Delta(b, a) \\ &= \max_{b \in B} \min_{a \in A} \| b - a \| \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Now Hausdorff distance can be defined as follows:

$$\Delta_{HD}(A, B) = \max(\Delta(A, B), \Delta(B, A)) \quad (5)$$

It measures the degree of mismatch between two sets by measuring the distance of a point of A that is the farthest from any point of B and vice versa. Hausdorff distance is simple, but it is very sensitive to the noise and occlusion. In order to overcome this problem many researchers modified Hausdorff distance namely partial Hausdorff distance (Huttenlocher et al. [6]), Modified Hausdorff distance (Dubussion and Jain [7]), Weighted Hausdorff distance (Lu et al. [12]) and so on. Of all these most famous distance measure is Modified Hausdorff distance. Dubussion and Jain [7] presented 24 different measures based on their behavior in the presence of the noise. It is less sensitive to the noise. Specially in their formulation

$$\Delta_{MHD}(A, B) = \max(\delta(A, B), \delta(B, A)) \quad (6)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \delta(A, B) &= \frac{1}{N_a} \sum_{a \in A} \Delta(a, B) \\ \delta(B, A) &= \frac{1}{N_b} \sum_{b \in B} \Delta(b, A) \end{aligned}$$

Here N_a and N_b are the cardinality of the set A and B respectively. Δ_{MHD} does not satisfy the triangle inequality property, so it is not a metric.

III. MODIFIED COMPLEMENT WEIGHTED SUM OF MINIMAL DISTANCE

The Sum of minimal distance measure (SMD) was proposed by Eiter and Mannila [8]. It is usually used in different applications of image processing. The Sum of Minimal distance [8] can be defined as

$$\Delta_{SMD}(A, B) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\sum_{a \in A} \Delta(a, B) + \sum_{b \in B} \Delta(b, A) \right) \quad (7)$$

SMD [8] performs best for registration of translated and noisy images whereas for the registration of rotated images it works better when compared with other distance measures. The generalization of the sum of minimal distances was introduced and its possible applications in image processing were explored by Lindblad et al. [20]. Symmetric, intensity interpolation-free, affine registration framework based on a combination of intensity and spatial information is proposed by Öfverstedt et al. [21].

Ćurić et al. [18] proposed complement weighted sum of minimal distance (CWSMD) between finite sets and evaluated its usefulness for shape registration and image processing. It is defined as follows as:

$$\Delta_{CWD}(A, B) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\sum_{a \in A} \Delta(a, B) \Delta(a, \bar{A})}{\sum_{a \in A} \Delta(a, \bar{A})} + \frac{\sum_{b \in B} \Delta(b, A) \Delta(b, \bar{B})}{\sum_{b \in B} \Delta(b, \bar{B})} \right) \quad (8)$$

where \bar{A} denotes the complement of set A with respect to the image space. In this set distance the contribution of each point of each set is weighted according to its distance to the complement of the set. Ćurić et al. [22] extended the Sum

of minimal distances and the Complement weighted sum of minimal distances to distances between fuzzy sets. Several families of distance measures [23] over images interpreted as fuzzy sets have been proposed and have shown an excellent performance for object recognition.

The complement weight of sum of minimal distance measure is applied over the gray scale image for image registration, there performance is low, so we introduce modified complement weighted sum of minimal distance (MCWSMD) (or) Δ_{MCWD} , in which we compute for each point a of set A , its contribution to the set distance by weighting $\Delta(a, B)$ by $(\Delta(a, \bar{A})\Delta(a, \bar{B}))$, that is the distance from a to the complement set A and it is multiplied with distance from a to the complement set B . Now the weight contribution of set A is normalised by the sum of all assigned weights. Similarly for set B , the contribution of all points are calculated. MCWSMD can be defined as follows as:

$$\Delta_{MCWD}(A, B) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\sum_{a \in A} \Delta(a, B) \Delta(a, \bar{A}) \Delta(a, \bar{B})}{\sum_{a \in A} \Delta(a, \bar{A}) \Delta(a, \bar{B})} + \frac{\sum_{b \in B} \Delta(b, A) \Delta(b, \bar{B}) \Delta(b, \bar{A})}{\sum_{b \in B} \Delta(b, \bar{B}) \Delta(b, \bar{A})} \right) \quad (9)$$

Modified complement weighted sum of minimal distance satisfies properties such as non negativity, separability, and symmetry but it does not satisfy the triangle inequality therefore it is a semi-metric. $\Delta(a, B)$ is calculated row wise, as the minimum of all row norms between a and rows of B . It gives norm of row difference. The complement is computed with respect to maximum intensity (255).

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The modified complement weighted sum of minimal distance is used for registration on grayscale images, medical images and also on the face dataset. In order to evaluate the performance of MCWSMD for registration, it is also used on binary images and the results are compared with a set of distance measures such as Hausdorff distance, modified Hausdorff distance, sum of minimal distance and with complement weighted sum of minimal distance measure as reported by Ćurić et al. [18]. Now, we present a greedy search algorithm [18] which we have used in our optimization process. It is described as follows:

- 1) Let I_S and I_T be source and target images respectively.
- 2) Initialize the variable $i=0$;
- 3) Repeat the steps below if $\Delta(\mathfrak{S}(I_T, P_i), I_S) < \Delta(\mathfrak{S}(I_T, P_{i-1}), I_S)$
 - a) Increment i by 1;
 - b) Perform the image registration using the minimization process defined as follows:
 $P_i = \arg \min_{P' \in N(P_{i-1}, \delta P)} \Delta(\mathfrak{S}(I_T, P'), I_S)$;
- 4) P_i is assigned to registration transformation vector P_r .

Fig. 1. Different Noise condition (a)-(d) Original Noise Free images (e)-(h) Images with Pepper Noise (i)-(l) Images with Salt Pepper Noise (m)-(p) Images with Missing Parts

Here $\mathfrak{S}(I_T, P')$ is the two dimensional geometric transformation of the target image I_T , that is defined by a parameter vector P' taken from the set P , Δ is the set distance. $N(p, \delta P) = \{p' : p' = p + \delta p, \delta p \in \delta P\}$ where δP is the set of unit parameter steps. This algorithm stops when no lower distance measure is found.

A. Performance evaluation on grayscale images

In order to evaluate the performance of the proposed Modified complement weighted sum of minimal distance, first, we conducted experiments on grayscale images. The source image is represented by I_S . It is displaced by different transformations and distorted by different types of noise, which are used as target images. Here the parameter vector is $P = (x, y, \theta)$ where (x, y) represents the translations along the axes and θ represents the rotation of the image. The three displacement vectors are denoted as D_i , where $i = 1, 2, 3$. The (x, y) components of each displacement vector $P_i = (x, y, \theta)$ are expressed in terms of one fourth of the width of the image W and one fourth of the height of the image H . The three displacement vectors used here are:

- (i) **Small Displacement:**
 $D_1 = \{(x, y, \theta) : x \in \{-0.1W, 0, 0.1W\},$
 $y \in \{-0.1H, 0, 0.1H\},$
 $\theta \in \{-20^\circ, 0^\circ, 20^\circ\}\} / \{(0, 0, 0^\circ)\}$

TABLE I

PERCENTAGE OF IMAGE REGISTRATION RESULTS FOR DIFFERENT DISPLACEMENT VECTORS D_1 , D_2 AND D_3 FOR GRAYSCALE AND MEDICAL IMAGES

Distance	Pepper	Salt Pepper	Missing	No noise
D_1				
	Grayscale	images		
Δ_{MCWSMD}	89.26	92.59	98.15	99.26
Δ_{CWD}	41.85	72.96	89.26	91.53
	Medical	images		
Δ_{MCWSMD}	94.07	89.26	98.52	97.04
Δ_{CWD}	44.44	75.93	98.89	96.23
D_2				
	Grayscale	images		
Δ_{MCWSMD}	87.78	91.85	99.26	100
Δ_{CWD}	24.07	72.96	90	92.33
	Medical	images		
Δ_{MCWSMD}	94.07	91.85	99.63	95.56
Δ_{CWD}	41.48	75.56	95.56	94.35
D_3				
	GrayScale	images		
Δ_{MCWSMD}	95.06	97.53	97.94	95.06
Δ_{CWD}	15.93	70.37	75.19	70.56
	Medical	images		
Δ_{MCWSMD}	95.93	96.67	98.52	99.63
Δ_{CWD}	10.74	43.70	98.89	95.55

TABLE II

COMPARISON OF MAXIMUM PERCENTAGE OF BINARY IMAGE REGISTRATION RESULTS FOR DIFFERENT DISPLACEMENT VECTORS D_{B1} , D_{B2} AND D_{B3}

Distance	Pepper	Salt Pepper	Missing	No noise
D_{B1}				
Δ_{HD}	90.10	69.85	35.24	99.13
Δ_{MHD}	97.98	96.35	97.79	98.37
Δ_{SMD}	98.17	97.88	98.08	98.17
Δ_{CWD}	98.27	98.37	94.33	98.65
Δ_{MCWSMD}	99.26	83.33	99.26	66.67
D_{B2}				
Δ_{HD}	72.50	43.37	27.69	80.96
Δ_{MHD}	89.42	89.04	85.87	89.52
Δ_{SMD}	89.71	90.38	89.90	89.71
Δ_{CWD}	89.81	90.10	86.35	90.10
Δ_{MCWSMD}	96.30	93.33	94.44	96.30
D_{B3}				
Δ_{HD}	48.57	16.15	2.31	56.73
Δ_{MHD}	80.46	76.92	80.87	80.96
Δ_{SMD}	79.08	82.08	81.15	82.12
Δ_{CWD}	80.96	80.96	78.85	82.98
Δ_{MCWSMD}	97.78	99.26	98.52	99.63

(ii) **Medium Displacement:**

$$D_2 = \{(x, y, \theta) : x \in \{-0.3W, 0, 0.3W\}, \\ y \in \{-0.3H, 0, 0.3H\}, \\ \theta \in \{-40^\circ, 0^\circ, 40^\circ\}\} / \{(0, 0, 0^\circ)\}$$

(iii) **Large Displacement:**

$$D_3 = \{(x, y, \theta) : x \in \{-1.2W, 0, 1.2W\}, \\ y \in \{-1.2H, 0, 1.2H\}, \\ \theta \in \{-60^\circ, 0^\circ, 60^\circ\}\} / \{(0, 0, 0^\circ)\}$$

Similar displacement vectors are used by Ćurić et al. [18] for binary images. The translation coordinates x and y are rounded to the nearest lower integer and rotated image is computed using nearest neighbor interpolation.

The source images are distorted by different types of noise such as salt and pepper noise, pepper noise and missing parts. The performance of registration is measured by using the distorted images with following types of noise:

Pepper noise: 5% of pixels in the images are reassigned as black (0).

Salt and Pepper noise: 1% of pixels in the image are affected by the salt and pepper noise with equal probability.

Missing parts: Two boundary pixels b_1 and b_2 of size 11×11 such that $b_1 \neq b_2$ are randomly selected and cropped from the image.

For grayscale images we have taken 20 images of size 256×256 and each one is displaced by D_i , $i = 1, 2, 3$, providing $3(3^3 - 1) = 78$ displacements. They are distorted by three selected noise types and one noise free image, so that we have 4 types of source image with distortion and hence the total will be $20 \cdot 78 \cdot 4 = 7,800$ images. These were tested for registering the source image with the target image. The registration results are tabulated in Table I. In this table all the values are presented in terms of percentage that is $(\text{number of images registered} / \text{total number of images tested}) \times 100$. When the target image is displayed by D_3 displacement vector, the registration results are better for the pepper noise and salt and pepper noise, whereas for missing parts it performs well for D_1 and D_2 displacement vector. For the noise free images, it gives 100% registration result when the target image is displaced by D_2 displacement vector. In Fig. 1, the synthetic, grayscale, medical and face images and their distortions are shown. First row consists of the noise free images, second row are added with pepper noise, third row added with salt and pepper noise and fourth row with the missing parts.

B. Performance evaluation on medical image

In this section, we evaluate the performance of modified complement weighted sum of minimal distance on medical images. The same set of displacement vectors is applied to

Fig. 2. Distance measure values between each of source image and target image (a) - (b) Pepper Noise (c) - (d) Salt and Pepper Noise (e) - (f) Missing Parts (g) - (h) Noise Free

the source image as described in previous section IV-A. 20 medical images [24] of size 256×256 are used to test the performance. Totally 7,800 images are used to register the target image with source image. The registration results are tabulated in Table I. For the pepper noise, salt and pepper noise and no noise, when the images are displaced by D_3 , the proposed measure gives better registration results, 95.93% 96.67% and 99.63% respectively, whereas for the missing parts, it gives good registration results at D_2 displacement vector.

C. Performance evaluation on synthetic image

Now we evaluate the performance on binary images. Since we used 40 binary images [25] as in Ćurić et al. [18], we compared 15,800 images to evaluate its performance. The three displacement vectors are used as described in [18] and are described follows as:

- (i) **Small Displacement:**
 $D_{B1} = \{(x, y, \theta) : x \in \{-0.1W, 0, 0.1W\},$
 $y \in \{-0.1H, 0, 0.1H\},$
 $\theta \in \{-5^\circ, 0^\circ, 5^\circ\} / \{(0, 0, 0^\circ)\}$
- (ii) **Medium Displacement:**
 $D_{B2} = \{(x, y, \theta) : x \in \{-0.3W, 0, 0.3W\},$
 $y \in \{-0.3H, 0, 0.3H\},$
 $\theta \in \{-20^\circ, 0^\circ, 20^\circ\} / \{(0, 0, 0^\circ)\}$
- (iii) **Large Displacement:**
 $D_{B3} = \{(x, y, \theta) : x \in \{-1.2W, 0, 1.2W\},$
 $y \in \{-1.2H, 0, 1.2H\},$
 $\theta \in \{-40^\circ, 0^\circ, 40^\circ\} / \{(0, 0, 0^\circ)\}$

Here W and H are expressed in terms of width, and height of the object in images. The registration results are compared with some of the existing methods namely Hausdorff distance, modified Hausdorff distance, sum of minimal distance and complement weighted sum of minimal distance and are tabulated in Table II. In this table, best performing distance measure for each noise condition is shown in bold. From this we can conclude that the proposed modified complement weighted sum of minimal distance performs better than existing measures expect at D_{B1} displacement vector for salt and pepper noise and noise free images. Second best distance measure is complement weighted sum of minimal distance and it is followed by Hausdorff distance measure.

D. Performance evaluation on Face recognition

To demonstrate the applicability of the proposed MCWSMD measure on face recognition, we have used the method on a large set of frontal views of human faces [26] which consists of 100 images. We carried out our experiment on different types

Fig. 3. (a) 023.jpg image with four boundary pixels (4 - 11×11 neighborhoods) missing and (b) Lowest distance measure for each image

of noise added images and also with noise free images. Here the displacement vector is not used. From the dataset, we have taken one image for instance *023.jpg* as source image with pepper noise, and then the MCWSMD distance between the source image with all the target images are computed. From these values, the lowest distance measure is determined and its corresponding target image is identified. For pepper noise added *023.jpg* image the lowest distance measure is 245.87. Similarly we have performed the experiments on different types of noise added images and on noise free images and

the results are shown in Fig. 2. For missing parts, we have used four boundary pixels and carried out the experiments and compared it with two boundary pixels of missing parts, the results are shown in the Fig. 3. When the number of boundary pixels increases there is increase in the distance measure value.

V. CONCLUSION

We have proposed a new distance measure called modified complement weighted sum of minimal distance (MCWSMD) measure for image registration. For synthetic images the proposed measure MCWSMD outperforms the other existing distance measures. Further, the performance is better for grayscale and medical images in presence of noise. It is also powerful measure in recognizing a face in a large face dataset. Thus we conclude that MCWSMD is less sensitive to noise and can be used in applications for image registration.

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